

Wave interaction with low mound breakwaters using a RANS model

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Abstract

Using COBRAS-UC, an improved version of the COBRAS (Cornell Breaking Waves and Structures) based on the Volume Averaged Reynolds Average Navier-Stokes (VARANS) equations, 2-D wave interaction with low mound breakwaters is analyzed. The model uses a Volume of Fluid Technique (VOF) method to capture the free surface which allows the modelling of complicated processes such as breakwater overtopping. Furthermore, thanks to the VARANS equations, the flow in the permeable layers underneath the caisson is quantitatively correct. In order to validate the model's performance, a new set of experimental studies are carried out in a wave flume at a 1:20 scale using regular and irregular waves. Comparisons between numerical and experimental free surface and pressure time histories and spectra under regular and irregular waves show a good agreement. Further comparisons of numerically predicted overtopping magnitudes with existing semi-empirical formulae and experimental data indicate that the model can be used as a complementary tool for the functional design of this kind of structures.

CE Data Base Subject Headings: breakwaters; wave overtopping; numerical analysis; coastal structures

Introduction

Coastal structures are built to protect coastal areas from erosion and flooding, as well as to shelter ports and marinas from wave action. The wave and structure interaction process depends on incident wave conditions and the structure typology.

In order to provide design guidelines for the hydraulic response of coastal structures, many semi-empirical formulations based on flume and basin experiments have been developed in the past. Such formulae try to consider and parameterize the most relevant variables ruling the process occurring in the wave and structure interaction phenomenon, mainly, reflection, run-up, rundown, overtopping and transmission. An extensive number of very successful semi-empirical formulations are available in the literature and can be found, as part of the state of the art in coastal structures design, in several books and manuals (f.e. Burcharth and Hughes, 2006).

As said, semi-empirical formulations, based on flume or wave basin experiments, cover a limited number of typologies and setups. Furthermore, many of them are based on a reduced set of incident wave conditions, which may lead to uncertainties and errors if used out of range, a problem often faced in current design or pre-design conditions.

In recent years, computational modeling of wave interaction with coastal structures is becoming an important complementary approach, especially when pre-designing the hydraulic response of some typologies of coastal structures.

The numerical model ability to analyze wave and structure interaction problems successfully depends mainly on the equations and solving techniques used, Losada (2003). Moreover, the leap to its application to real case studies requires computational robustness and efficiency in terms of computation as well as a thorough validation process only available today for a limited set of models.

According to the existing literature, the most relevant numerical models currently available for wave and coastal structures interaction are different versions of models solving the nonlinear shallow equations; models based on Reynolds Average Navier-Stokes equations including any kind of free surface-tracking or –capturing technique and, more recently, particle methods like the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH), in which the governing partial differential equations of continuum fluid dynamics, are transformed into particle form by integral equations through the use of an interpolation function that gives kernel estimation of the field variables at a point.

Models based on the nonlinear shallow water equations (NSWE), are derived on the assumption of hydrostatic pressure and are obtained by vertically integrating the Navier-Stokes equations, i.e. Kobayashi and Wurjanto (1989), Mingham and Causson (1998), Hu et al. (2000), Hubbard and Dodd (2002), Stansby and Feng (2004). The use of NSWE places severe restrictions on real applications inherent, essentially, to the intrinsic requirement to satisfy the shallow water limit. This restriction is especially crude when considering high frequency components in the incident wave spectrum and also requires locating the offshore boundary condition of the numerical model close to the structure. Other restrictions are associated with the semi-empirical introduction of breaking, porous flow modeling or the difficulty in simulating complicated free surfaces. However, they are computationally very efficient in providing the chance to simulate wave trains including about 1000 waves very rapidly, which may be of importance, for example, to analyze extreme statistics of wave overtopping.

Inherent limitation of the shallow water limit, may be overcome considering the application of modified Boussinesq equations for wave and structure interactions (e.g. Lynett et al., 2000). However, the computational effort required to solve these equations has discouraged researchers to use them for real applications.

During the last years particle methods such as the Moving Particle Semi-Implicit (MPS) method of Koshizuka et al. (1995); or the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method in its different versions (i.e. Dalrymple et al., 2001; Gotoh et al., 2004, and Shao, 2006) have become very popular. Being based on a grid-less Lagrangian approach, they are able to track accurately large deformations of the free surface. However, whether or not the weakly incompressible or the incompressible SPH method is used, this technique has several disadvantages. The high number of particles required to obtain a reliable solution; the use of fixed particle spacing; the limited validation available and a very low computational efficiency are some of the issues that need to be solved before considering SPH for practical purposes.

Free of some of the limitations mentioned above, numerical models based on the Navier-Stokes equations (NSE) have received considerable attention in the last decade applied to the analysis of wave interaction with coastal structures under breaking conditions, as they allow the calculation of the velocity field in the whole computational domain for any type of flow, whether rotational or irrotational.

Among existing NSE models, RANS-based equation models are nowadays the more suitable tool to analyze the wave structure interaction problem. The analysis of wave interaction with porous structures lies in the fact that they take into account the turbulence generation/dissipation mechanisms inside the porous media and also in the wave breaking process. The introduction of the turbulent effects constitutes a true stumbling block for the modeling of wave-structure interaction with permeable breakwaters. Among other RANS models available in literature (i.e.: Troch and de Rouck, 1998; Kawasaki, 1999; Li et al., 2004), COBRAS is probably the most extensively validated, especially for wave structure interaction.

Lin and Liu (1998), based on a previously existing model called RIPPLE (Kothe et al., 1991), presented COBRAS (Cornell Breaking Waves and Structures) for simulating breaking waves and wave interaction with coastal structures. In this work, a modified and improved version of COBRAS, named COBRAS-UC (Losada et al., 2007; Torres-Freyermuth et al, 2007) is used to investigate the interaction of regular and irregular waves with low mound breakwaters focusing on the hydraulic response of the structure. The paper is organized as follows. The main characteristics of COBRAS-UC are presented in the following section. The experimental set-up carried out for the model validation is presented in Section 3. Section 4 is devoted to the explanation of the numerical setup and model calibration. In Section 5 the numerical model is tested and verified with the experimental data by comparing free surface and pressure time series, wave spectra and several overtopping related magnitudes. In section 6, an application of the model to wave overtopping analysis is carried out. Concluding remarks are presented in the last section.

Mathematical formulation

Equations in the Fluid Domain

COBRAS-UC (Losada et al., 2007) solves the 2DV Reynolds Average Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations, based on the decomposition of the instantaneous velocity, u , and pressure field, p , into mean, $\bar{\cdot}$, and turbulent components, $'$,

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial t} + \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} + g_i + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{\tau}_{ij}}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial (\overline{u'_i u'_j})}{\partial x_j} \quad (2)$$

and the k - ε equations for the turbulent kinetic energy (k), and the turbulent dissipation rate, (ε),

$$\frac{\partial k}{\partial t} + \overline{u_j} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\frac{\nu_t}{\sigma_k} + \nu \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] - \overline{(u'_i u'_j)} \frac{\partial \overline{u_i}}{\partial x_j} - \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial t} + \overline{u_j} \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_j} = & \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\frac{\nu_t}{\sigma_\varepsilon} + \nu \right) \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_j} \right] \\ & + C_{1\varepsilon} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} \nu_t \left(\frac{\partial \overline{u_i}}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \overline{u_j}}{\partial x_i} \right) \frac{\partial \overline{u_i}}{\partial x_j} - C_{2\varepsilon} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $i, j=1, 2$ for a two-dimensional flow, ρ is the density of fluid, g_i the i^{th} component of the gravitational acceleration, $\overline{\tau_{ij}}$ is the viscous stress tensor of the mean flow, and ν_t is the eddy viscosity. For a Newtonian fluid, $\overline{\tau_{ij}} = 2\mu\overline{\sigma_{ij}}$, with μ being the molecular viscosity and $\overline{\sigma_{ij}} = \frac{1}{2}(\partial\overline{u_i}/\partial x_j + \partial\overline{u_j}/\partial x_i)$, the rate of strain tensor of the mean flow.

The influence of turbulence fluctuations on the mean flow field is represented by the Reynolds stresses $\rho\overline{(u'_i u'_j)}$. The governing equations for k - ε are derived from the Navier-Stokes equations and higher order correlations of turbulence fluctuations in k and ε equations are replaced by closure conditions. The empirical coefficients ($C_{1\varepsilon}=1.44$; $C_{1k}=1.92$; $\sigma_\varepsilon=1.3$ and $\sigma_k=1.0$) were experimentally determined from stationary flows, Rodi (1980). A nonlinear algebraic Reynolds stress model is used to relate the Reynolds stress tensor and the strain rate of mean flow (see Rodi, 1980, and Lin and Liu, 1998, for details). The movement of free surface is tracked by the Volume of Fluid (VOF) method.

Equations for the Flow in the Porous Media

The main assumption of the COBRAS-UC model consists in considering that the RANS equations coupled with an appropriate turbulence model (in the present case, the k - ε model) can adequately describe the flow field in the porous media. Given the complex structure of porous materials, the direct resolution of the intrinsic flow field inside the pores is still not practical.

Consequently, the flow in porous media is obtained in the COBRAS-UC model through the resolution of the Volume-Averaged Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (VARANS) equations, see Hsu *et al.* (2002) for the complete mathematical formulation. These equations are derived by integration of the RANS equations over a control volume. The mathematical process of volume averaging of a certain quantity a is defined by the following expression:

$$\langle a \rangle = \frac{1}{V_f} \int_{V_f} a dV \quad (5)$$

where $\langle \rangle$ denotes the intrinsic volume averaging, V is the total averaging volume, V_f is the volume in V which is occupied by the fluid phase and $\langle a \rangle$ is the averaged magnitude. The intrinsic averaging operator defined by equation (5) can be related to Darcy's volume averaging operator defined as follows:

$$\langle a \rangle_D = \frac{1}{V} \int_{V_f} a dV \quad (6)$$

through the simple relationship: $\langle a \rangle_D = n \langle a \rangle$, where $n = V_f/V$, is the porosity and is assumed for simplicity to be a constant in the present model. In terms of velocity, $\langle a \rangle_D$ would be the seepage velocity and $\langle a \rangle$ the filtration velocity. Hereafter, unless specified, volume averaging will be understood as intrinsic volume averaging, as defined in expression (5).

The VARANS equations are obtained by applying the intrinsic volume average to the RANS equations. The ensemble averaged velocity of the RANS equations (mass and momentum) are assumed to be:

$$\frac{\partial \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle}{\partial t} + \frac{\langle \bar{u}_j \rangle}{1+c_A} \frac{\partial \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle}{\partial x_j} = \frac{1}{\rho(1+c_A)} \left[-\frac{\partial \langle \bar{p} \rangle}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial \rho \langle u'_i u'_j \rangle}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \langle \bar{\tau}_{ij} \rangle}{\partial x_j} + \rho g_i \right] \\ - \frac{1}{1+c_A} \left[\frac{\alpha \nu (1-n)^2}{n^2 D_{50}^2} \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle + \frac{\beta (1-n)}{n D_{50}^2} \sqrt{\langle \bar{u}_1 \rangle^2 + \langle \bar{u}_2 \rangle^2} \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle \right] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In the VARANS equations, the interfacial forces between the fluid and solids have been modeled by the extended Forchheimer relationship, in which both linear and nonlinear drag forces are included in the last term of equation (8).

The expression used in the model for the linear and nonlinear drag forces is given by,

$$I = \frac{\alpha \nu (1-n)^2}{n^2 D_{50}^2} \bar{u} + \frac{\beta (1-n)}{n^2 D_{50}} \bar{u} |\bar{u}| \quad (9)$$

where α and β are the only two empirical parameters used in the calibration of the numerical model, n is the porosity, ν the kinematic viscosity and \bar{u} stands for velocity. An additional parameter, c_A affecting the inertia term is included in the formulation to take into account the added mass. The precise descriptions of the α and β coefficients are still not fully understood for oscillatory flows. They depend on several parameters such as the Reynolds number, the shape of the stones, the grade of the porous material, the permeability and of course, the flow characteristics. Based on previous work, we have experienced (Garcia *et al.* 2004 and Lara *et al.* 2006a,b) that, under oscillatory flow and waves propagating over slopes or breaking, values existing in the literature may not be valid since the experimental conditions for obtaining those formulae did not take into account these effects. Detailed discussions on the numerical algorithms, initial and boundary conditions can be found in Lin and Liu (1998) and Hsu *et al.* (2002).

Over the last years, the model has been under a continuous development process based on an extensive validation procedure, carried out for low-crested structures (Garcia *et al.* 2004, Losada *et al.* 2005 and Lara *et al.* 2006a), wave breaking on permeable slopes (Lara *et al.* 2006b), overtopping on rubble mound breakwaters (Losada *et al.*, 2007) or surf zone on natural beaches (Torres-Freyermuth *et al.*, 2007). A number of modifications have been introduced into the original COBRAS code at the University of Cantabria in order to overcome some of the initial limitations and especially to convert

it into a tool for practical application. The improvements cover the wave generation process; code updating and refactoring; optimization and improvement of the main subroutines; improvement of input and output data definition and the development of a graphical user interface and output data processing programs.

With the aforementioned modifications being implemented, the computational cost of the model has been reduced by 40 % compared to the initial code for a typical run, and several error sources leading to execution problems have been eliminated opening the possibility to consider larger and more complex computational domains and longer simulation times.

In this paper, further validation of the model is carried out by considering random wave interaction with low-mound breakwaters. Free surface, pressure and wave overtopping are analyzed based on the numerical model and compared with experimental results.

Description of the experimental set up

A set of experiments on wave interaction with a low mound breakwater were carried out in the wave flume of the University of Cantabria. The flume is 60.5 m long, 2 m wide and 2 m high. At one side of the wave flume, a mixed piston-pendulum type wave maker has attached two free surface wave gauges integrated in an Active Wave Absorption System (AWACS®) that allows the absorption of reflected waves. At the rear end of the wave flume, three dissipative ramps were placed to absorb the transmitted waves.

The breakwater (see Figure 1) is built out of an impermeable caisson installed on a rubble mound foundation. The impermeable caisson is 1.04 m long, 0.3 m high and 2 m wide. The still water level was 0.8 m and the structure freeboard was 0.2 m. A 0.3 m high, $D_{50} = 0.035$ cm and $1V/2H$ gravel foundation was placed below the breakwater. The foundation layer was covered with an external layer of gravel with $D_{50} = 3.5$ cm. At

the seaside face of the structure, a 10 cm berm was built. The porosity was 0.48 for the foundation layer and 0.50 for the outer layers.

Figure 1. Experimental set-up. Data in meters.

Free surface evolution was measured using resistive gauges (WG) located along the flume. These were placed along the centreline of the wave flume in order to measure free surface time series. Ten wave gauges were located in front of the structure, 3 were used to evaluate the reflection coefficient. Three additional wave gauges were placed on the top of the caisson to measure the thickness of the water layer during the overtopping events. One wave gauge was placed at the leeward side of the structure to control water level in the flume. Finally, a reservoir was built at the crown of the structure in order to collect the water which overtops the structure. The top of the reservoir was aligned with the upper face of the caisson so as not to interfere with the flow. The box only occupied a third of the width of the wave flume, allowing most of the overtopped flow to reach the leeward side of the structure. A resistive wave gauge placed inside the pool recorded the free surface variation. The overtopping discharge was evaluated by measuring the water volume jumps in the reservoir of each overtopping wave. The water depth multiplied by the horizontal area of the reservoir (0.69 m^2) gives the instantaneous volume of water inside the box.

Six pressure transducers (PG) were installed at the front wall and four underneath the caisson to measure pressure time series, sampled at 60 Hz. Figure 1 presents the experimental set-up.

Regular and irregular waves were considered in the experiments. Fifth-order Stokes waves were generated for the regular wave cases. A JONSWAP-type spectrum ($\gamma=3.3$) was considered for the random wave tests. The total number of different wave

conditions was 20 for regular and 25 for random waves. Table 1 presents target wave conditions in the experimental setup.

Table 1. Target parameters for generated waves

Numerical model setup and calibration

Following the experimental setup and previous experience in the application of the numerical model, incident waves are generated by an internal wave generator able to generate regular and irregular waves, (Lara et al. 2006a).

The choice of grid size varies in the y -direction from 1 cm above the SWL (region 1) to 3 cm under the SWL (region 2). In the x -direction a coarser grid size, 5 cm, is used in the generation region, increasing the resolution up to 2 cm in the vicinity of the breakwater, which is the area of interest (region 3). A total number of 92 grids are used in the y -direction, while in the x -direction 2325 grids are used. Other grid resolutions have been tested in order to evaluate the computational time and the accuracy of the results. Using a resolution of 0.5 cm in both the horizontal and vertical direction increases computational time to a factor of 30 with not much improvement in the accuracy of the results but with a better definition of the tongue of water overtopping the structure.

A sponge layer has been located in Region 1 in order to absorb the energy reflected on the structure and the waves generated by the internal source function in the offshore direction, requiring a numerical domain 25 meters longer than the laboratory wave flume.

The only calibration parameters used in this model are the α (linear drag parameter) and β (non-linear drag parameter) coefficients of the porous flow model (see Garcia et al. 2004, Lara et al. 2006a, Lara et al. 2006b), as the remaining coefficient

regarding the added mass, c_A is set to be 0.34 based on previous experience. In this work the best-fit values for α and β are evaluated by comparing experimental data and numerical results of free surface and pressure time series for two regular wave cases: (1) $H=0.1$ m and $T= 3$ s and (2) $H= 0.1$ m and $T= 5$ s.

After a trial and error process, the best-fit parameter values calculated were $\alpha = 200$ and $\beta = 0.8$ for the foundation core and $\alpha = 200$ and $\beta = 1.1$ for the external layer. Numerical results appeared to be more sensitive to the nonlinear drag coefficient β than to the linear drag parameter α , because the flow is mainly turbulent within the porous media. These values of the coefficients remain unchanged for all the other regular and irregular simulated wave cases.

Model validation

Model validation is carried out by comparing the numerical results with experimental measurements as well as with semi-empirical formulations for some of the functional parameters for several regular and irregular cases.

Free surface time series

Results of free surface time series are presented in figures 2 to 4 for three different tests: a regular wave case ($H=0.25$ m and $T=3$ s); and two irregular wave cases: (1) $H_s=0.21$ m and $T_p=3$ s and (2) $H_s=0.18$ m and $T_p=5$ s; where H_s and T_p are the significant wave height and peak period, respectively.

Results are presented for seven positions, four in front of the structure and three over the crown.

Figure 2 shows the free surface time histories from both the numerical model and experimental data for regular waves ($H=0.25$ m and $T=3$ s) at the different locations

along the flume. Plotted results include a simulation time of 160 seconds with approximately 50 waves in the time series. The agreement between the numerical results and the measurements for both wave phase and height is very good. The model is able to simulate the quasi-standing wave pattern with an antinode located at the caisson and the node close to WG7. Waves increase their steepness without breaking as they propagate towards the structure and exceed the structure freeboard, consequently inducing a regular overtopping process. This can be clearly seen in the time series of WG11 to WG13. In WG11 the model is able to capture the overtopping events with a perfect match in phase. Small variations can be seen in the amplitude with a general tendency of the model to slightly underestimate the measured free surface. Even if the fluid layer on the top of the structure is very thin, the model is able to predict the measured free surface time series well in terms of phase and reasonably well when considering the amplitudes.

Figure 2. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Regular wave case: $H=0.25\text{m}$ $T=3\text{s}$

Figures 3 and 4 correspond to the measurements and numerical solutions for the free surface time series at 7 different positions for irregular wave cases with different significant wave heights and peak periods. As expected, the irregular wave cases are more difficult to model. For $H_s=0.21\text{ m}$ and $T_p=3\text{ s}$ case, slight variations between measured and predicted free surface already appear in WG7 but, in general, the agreement is good. One source of these slight deviations could be the high reflection induced by the structure, almost 90%, which may increase the differences between the numerical absorption based on a sponge layer and the way active absorption in the flume deals with high reflection. The combined effect of reflection and shoaling results in a general increase of wave amplitudes in the time series as waves propagate towards

the structure. In WG8, WG9 and WG10, the model is able to predict the free surface time history with reasonable accuracy. In WG10 the highest waves, reaching wave heights in the range of 60 cm, attack the structure without breaking. In front of the structure, the model tends to overestimate measured wave heights, which results in an overestimation of the number and magnitude of overtopping events as can be seen in WG11 ($t=70$ s - 85 s and $t=170$ s – 180 s). This problem is also evident in WG12 and WG13.

For the longer peak period and lower significant wave height, $H_s=0.18$ m and $T_p=5$ s (figure 4), numerical results show a general improvement with a good agreement for measured free surface time series. An overestimation of wave height is visible in some waves of the record, resulting in an overprediction of some overtopping events as seen in WG11.

In conclusion, it can be said that the general agreement between experimental and numerical free surface time series is good for both regular and irregular waves.

Figure 3. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Irregular wave case: $H_s=0.21$ m $T_p=3$ s

Figure 4. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Irregular wave case: $H_s=0.18$ m $T_p=5$ s

Wave energy spectra

Figure 5 shows the wave energy spectra evolution along the centerline of the wave flume for a $H_s=0.18$ m and $T_p=5$ s case. Comparison of the numerical and measured spectral shape shows a general good agreement in the 13 locations considered except for minor overpredictions of the energy contents in some of the superharmonics.

Due to the reflection process at the structure, a partial standing wave system is established with a node close to WG6 and an antinode at the structure. The zero moment

wave height presents a mean error between the numerical and experimental value of about 8%.

Figure 5. Free surface spectra, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Irregular wave case: $H_s=0.18\text{m}$ $T_p=5\text{s}$

In order to provide a clearer insight into the behavior of the numerical model along the wave flume, a spectral analysis has been carried out. Zero-order moment wave height has been evaluated at different positions along the wave flume for both regular and irregular wave test, for the purpose of analyzing the ability of the model in simulating wave energy evolution. The whole set of numerically simulated cases (14 for regular waves and 18 for irregular waves) has been compared with the experimental records. Figures 6 and 7 show the comparisons for regular and irregular wave test respectively. Each of the presented panels displays results for the entire simulated and recorded set of cases at the gauges location in front of the caisson. The panel at the bottom right bottom of figures 6 and 7 display the zero-order moment wave height at all the recorded locations and includes all the tested cases.

Results confirm that the model predicts very well the wave energy distribution along the flume. The accuracy is quite good, not only at the vicinity of the structure but also at the far field. Slight differences in the accuracy of the results have been found according to the wave characteristics (regular or irregular). The relative error for all tested cases has been calculated to be less than 5%, yielding -3.29% for regular and -0.61% for irregular waves. The standard deviation of the relative error has been found to be $\pm 8.04\%$ and $\pm 6.88\%$, for regular and irregular waves, respectively showing a narrow deviation band of the results.

Should be noticed that the error has been evaluated as the difference of the computed and the measured value and divided all by the measured value.

Figure 6. Zero-moment wave height. Laboratory and numerical comparison – Regular wave cases

Figure 7. Zero-moment wave height. Laboratory and numerical comparison – Irregular wave cases

Pressures

Pressure time series underneath and at the seaward face of the caisson are investigated. Figure 8 shows comparisons between predicted and experimental pressure time series for case the following case: $H_s=0.18$ m and $T_p=5$ s. The upper panel in the plot presents the location of the 10 pressure gauges on the caisson. Comparisons show that the numerical model is able to represent with good accuracy the pressure time series except for minor deviations in magnitude for some of the waves. The model seems to deal very well with the porous flow underneath the caisson as can be seen in PG7 to PG10, which records depend completely on the flow passing through the rubble mound layers. It has to be pointed out that the porous flow parameters calibrated for two regular wave cases give outstanding results for irregular wave trains. Furthermore, numerical predictions of pressure at gauges PG5 and PG6, mostly registering only overtopping waves are also very good. A correct evaluation of the pressure time series at the caisson is a fundamental issue to address structure stability considering the numerical model.

Figure 8. Pressure time evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Irregular wave case: $H_s=0.18$ m $T_p=5$ s

Figure 9. Snapshots of instantaneous free surface, velocities and dynamic pressure. Irregular wave case: $H_s=0.18$ m $T_p=5$ s

Figure 9 shows simultaneous snapshots of free surface, velocities and pressure at four instants. The lower panel presents the comparison between the computed free surface time series and the experimental data. The left panel shows the comparison between the measured and calculated pressure law around the caisson at the selected

times. The agreement is very good, both in the fluid and in the rubble mound layers. In the right panels, snapshots of free surface and velocity fields are plotted. The velocity field is presented at four instants when the wave crest is reaching the structure. In the last panel at $t=128.5$ s, the velocity field induced by an overtopped wave is presented. It can be seen how the larger velocities are reached at the upper face of the caisson. This figure shows that the main contribution of the model to physical experiments is that it may provide: (1) information of relevant variables with higher resolution; (2) time series in locations where measurements are difficult or not possible to take and (3) information of non measured variables, such as in this particular case the velocity field.

Application of the model to wave overtopping analysis

A crucial potential application of the model is the evaluation of wave overtopping as one of the most relevant hydraulic parameters in the design of coastal structures. In this section, results obtained from the numerical model are compared with experimental results and existing wave overtopping formulae. Average overtopping discharge, percentage (probability) of overtopping waves and maximum overtopping volume per wave are considered in order to validate the model capability to simulate wave overtopping.

One of the main advantages of using COBRAS-UC is that it is able to provide time history of wave overtopping and therefore, provides the opportunity to analyze individual overtopping events which could be more important than the average discharge.

Analysis of average overtopping discharges

The accumulated overtopping discharge and the average discharge during the simulation period, Q_A , are shown in the figure 10 for three irregular wave cases: $H_s=0.21$ m and $T_p=3$ s (left), $H_s=0.18$ m and $T_p=5$ s (middle) and $H_s=0.18$ m and $T_p=6$ s (right).

Figure 10. Wave overtopping as a function of time.

In the three different cases, although minor differences exist, there is a good agreement between the numerical and experimental accumulated overtopping discharge time history has been found. Only during short interval periods, some differences appear in the time series of wave overtopping volumes, due to the fact that slight differences in wave height deviations in front of the structure induce significant changes in the overtopped amount of water, as shown before. The best agreement is found for the highest waves and shorter wave periods. Experimental and numerical results show that, since for the simulated cases the difference in wave height is small, overtopping is mostly controlled by the wave period.

The comparison between the numerical and experimental average discharge over the simulation period shown in the plots, indicates relatively small differences, proving the abilities of COBRAS-UC to simulate with a high degree of accuracy the wave overtopping process in complicated structures.

Figure 11 presents the average overtopping discharge values predicted by COBRAS-UC versus the experimental values for all the cases tested in the laboratory, including wave overtopping events. As can be seen, the model gives a good agreement showing a small general trend underestimating the experimental results, especially for small discharge values.

Figure 11 also includes results obtained from, semi-empirical formulae available in literature applicable to the typology studied in this work. Franco et al. (1994) considered several configurations including a vertical wall with and without a perforated front and a composite structure setup. The formulation by Besley (1999) is based on previous works by Bradbury and Allsop (1988) and Owen (1980) and considers low mound breakwaters among other typologies.

Results show that the best agreement between numerical and experimental results is obtained by COBRAS-UC. The mean error of the numerical model is -8.5% with a standard deviation of $\pm 25.66\%$. Franco et al. (1994) show a worse agreement with a mean error of -71.9%, with a standard deviation of $\pm 25.66\%$. Besley (1999) formulation exhibits similar results to those shown by Franco et al. (1994), with a mean error of -63.4%, and a standard deviation of $\pm 14.7\%$. In these typologies wave propagation is conditioned by the presence of the rubble mound, including the effect of pulsating waves.

Figure 11. Mean wave overtopping discharge – Comparison between semiempirical formulation, model and laboratory

Percentage of overtopping waves and maximum overtopping event

Overtopping events present a random distribution both in time and volume discharge and usually a few number of waves control the main part of the overtopped amount of water. According to Franco et al. (1994) and Franco and Franco (1999) the exceedance probability of each overtopping volume $P(V)$ can be calculated with a three-parameter Weibull distribution function, which is found to give a good statistical description of the data. This probability can be expressed in terms of 3 fitting coefficients A, B and C, which are the scale, shape and set-off fitting coefficients, respectively. The set-off coefficient C, represents the percentage (probability) of overtopping waves (N_{ow}/N_w), where N_{ow} and N_w are the number of overtopping waves and number of incident waves, respectively. Assuming the percentage of overtopping waves to be Rayleigh distributed, Franco et al. (1994) defines the following expression for C,

$$C = \frac{N_{ow}}{N_w} = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{1}{k} \frac{R_c}{H_s}\right)^2\right)$$

where, k is a best fitting constant recommended to be 0.91 for caisson breakwaters.

Figure 12b presents the comparison between probability of overtopping, represented by the set-off coefficient, C , observed in the laboratory versus the values predicted by the model and the formulation by Franco et al. (1994). The numerical results show a good agreement with the measurements as expected because the average overtopping discharges were correctly simulated. Cases with an overtopping probability of one or close to one correspond to highly energetic regular waves. Cases with a probability of zero or close to zero correspond to irregular and regular wave cases with low wave heights and consequently with no overtopping events.

Figure 12. (a) Comparison between experimental, numerical and semi-empirical results for maximum overtopping volume. (b) V_{max} Set-off coefficient $C=(N_{ow}/N_w)$ representing the percentage of overtopping wave. Comparison between numerical, semi-empirical and observed values.

The maximum overtopping event is an alternative parameter in the analysis of functionality since, in general, a few overtopping events may dominate the functionality performance of a coastal structure. Maximum overtopping event comparison is plotted on figure 12a showing a relatively good agreement with a general trend to underestimate the experimental values. COBRAS-UC shows a mean error of -13.5% with a standard deviation of $\pm 32\%$.

Conclusions and remarks

In this paper, the application of a model, named COBRAS-UC to the analysis of wave interaction with low-mound breakwaters is presented. The equations considered in the model allow the simulation of complex 2-D flows including transient, highly nonlinear waves, wave breaking and porous flow. The model allows long simulations

that can vary from hundreds to thousands of waves depending on resolution, in reasonable periods of time and on standard PCs. The numerical model has been validated against a set of experimental cases including regular and irregular waves. Results have shown that the model is capable of predicting the hydraulic response of the structure very well. Comparisons of predicted free surface and pressure time series are very good for all the simulated cases. Furthermore, the analysis of wave overtopping has also shown that COBRAS-UC has a high potential to become a complementary tool to analyze the hydraulic response of this typology of structures. It has been shown that the model may contribute to improve physical modeling by providing: (1) information of relevant variables with higher resolution; (2) time series in locations where measurements are difficult or not possible to take and (3) information of non *measured variables*

In order to improve the model's abilities and especially to provide important statistical information for the analysis of structure response, the computational efficiency of the model still requires improvement, since for certain scales and grid resolutions, simulations including about 1000 waves may require several days of computation on a standard PC. Regarding new processes, the introduction of air or 3-D effects might be of importance under some circumstances in the modeling.

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References

Besley, P., 1999. Overtopping of seawalls: design and assessment manual. Environment Agency. Bristol, R&D Technical Report No.W178, 1999, 37 pp CEM, Coastal Engineering Manual.

Bradbury, A.P. and Allsop, N.W.H., 1988. Hydraulic effects of breakwaters crown walls. Proc. Conference on Design of Breakwaters. Institution of Civil Engineering Thomas Telford, London, 385– 396.

Burcharth, H. F. and Hughes, S. A., 2006. Fundamentals of Design - Part 1, Chapter 1, 2 and 3. In: Vincent, L., and Demirbilek, Z. (editors), Coastal Engineering Manual, Part II, Hydrodynamics, Chapter II-2, Engineer Manual 1110-2-1100, U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Washington, DC.

Dalrymple, R.A., Knio, O., Cox, D.T., Gomez-Gesteira, M. and Zou, S., 2001. Using a Lagrangian particle method for deck overtopping. Proc. Waves ASCE 2001, pp. 1082– 1091.

Franco, C. and Franco, L., 1999. Overtopping Formulas for Caisson Breakwaters with nonbreaking 3D Waves. Journal of Waterway, Port, Coastal, and Ocean Engineering, American Society of Civil Engineers, Vol 125, No. 2, pp 98-108.

Franco, L., de Gerloni, M. and van der Meer, J.W., 1994. Wave overtopping on vertical and composite breakwaters. Proceedings of the 24th International Coastal Engineering Conference, American Society of Civil Engineers, Vol 1, pp 1030-1045.

- Garcia, N., Lara, J.L. and Losada, I.J., 2004. 2-D Numerical analysis of near-field flow at low-crested permeable breakwaters. *Coastal Engineering*, 51, 991-1020.
- Gotoh, H., Shao, S.D. and Memita, T., 2004. SPH-LES model for numerical investigation of wave interaction with partially immersed breakwater. *Coastal Engineering of Japan*. 46 (1), 39–63.
- Hsu, T.-J., Sakakiyama, T. and Liu, P.L.-F., 2002. A numerical model for wave motions and turbulence flows in front of a composite breakwater. *Coastal Engineering*, 46, 25-50.
- Hu, K., Mingham, C.G. and Causon, D.M., 2000. Numerical simulation of wave overtopping of coastal structures using the non-linear shallow water equations. *Coast. Eng.* 41, 433–465.
- Hubbard, M.E. and Dodd, N., 2002. A 2D numerical model of wave run-up and overtopping. *Coastal Engineering*, vol. 47, pp. 1-26.
- Kawasaki, K., 1999. Numerical simulation of breaking and post-breaking wave deformation process around a submerged breakwater. *Coastal Engineering Journal*, 41: 201-223.
- Kobayashi, N. and Wurjanto, A., 1989. Wave transmission over submerged breakwaters. *Journal of Waterways, Port, Coastal and Ocean Engineering*, 115: 662-680.
- Koshizuka, S., Tamako, H. and Oka, Y., 1995. A particle method for incompressible viscous flow with fluid fragmentation. *Comput. Fluid Dyn. J.* 4 (1), 29–46.
- Kothe, D. B., Mjolsness, R. C. and Torrey, M. D., 1991. RIPPLE: A computer program for incompressible flows with free surfaces. Los Alamos National Laboratory, LA-12007-S
- Lara, J.L., Garcia, N. and Losada, I.J., 2006a. RANS modelling applied to random wave interaction with submerged permeable structures. *Coastal Engineering*, 53, 395-417.

- Lara, J.L., Losada, I.J. and Liu, P.L.-F., 2006b. Breaking waves over a mild gravel slope: experimental and numerical analysis. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, AGU, Vol. 111, C11019; doi: 10-1029/2005 JC003374.
- Li, T., Troch, P. and De Rouck, J., 2004. Wave overtopping over a sea dike, *Journal of Computational Physics*. 198, 686-726.
- Lin, P.Z., and Liu, P.L.F., 1998. A numerical study of breaking waves in the surf zone. *J. Fluid Mech.* 359, 239–264.
- Losada, I.J., 2003. Advances in modeling the effects of permeable and reflective structures on waves and nearshore flows. In: *Advances in Coastal Modeling*. Elsevier Oceanography Series, Vol. 67. Ed. V. Chris Lakhan.
- Losada, I.J., Lara, J. L., Guanche, R. and Gonzalez-Ondina, J.M.,(2007) Numerical analysis of wave overtopping of rubble mound breakwaters, *Coastal Engineering*, (In Press), Available online 13 August 2007, doi:10.1016/j.coastaleng.2007.06.003.
- Losada, I.J., Lara, J.L, Damgaard, E., Garcia, N., 2005. Modelling of velocity and turbulence fields around and within low-crested rubble-mound breakwaters. *Coastal Engineering*, 52, 887-913.
- Lynett, P., Liu, P. L.-F., Losada, I.J., and Vidal, C., 2000. Solitary Wave Interaction with Porous Breakwaters, *Journal of Waterway, Port, Coastal, and Ocean Engineering* (ASCE), v. 126(6), p. 314-322.
- Mingham, C.G. and Causon, D.M., 1998. High-resolution finite-volume method for shallow water flows. *J. Hydraul. Eng.*, ASCE 124 (6), 605–614.
- Owen M. W., 1980. Design of sea walls allowing for wave overtopping. Report EX 924, Hydraulics Research, Wallingford.
- Rodi, W., 1980. Turbulence models and their application in hydraulics – a state-of-the-art review. IAHR Publication.

- Shao, S., 2006. Incompressible SPH simulation of wave breaking and overtopping with turbulence modeling. *Int. J. Numer. Meth. Fluids.* 50:597–621
- Stansby, P.K., Feng, T., 2004. Surf zone wave overtopping a trapezoidal structure: 1-D modelling and PIV comparison. *Coast. Eng.* 51, 483–500.
- Torres-Freyermuth, A., I. J. Losada, and J. L. Lara (2007), Modeling of surf zone processes on a natural beach using Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 112, C09014, doi:10.1029/2006JC004050.
- Troch, P., de Rouck, J., 1998. Development of two-dimensional numerical wave flume for wave interaction with rubble mound breakwaters. 26th Int. Coastal Eng. Conf., pp. 1638-1649.

Figure 1. Experimental set-up. Data in meters.

Figure 2. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ra35: $H=0.25\text{m}$ $T=3\text{s}$

Figure 3. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ia35: $H_s=0.21\text{m}$ $T_p=3\text{s}$

Figure 4. Free surface evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ia55: $H_s=0.18\text{m}$ $T_p=5\text{s}$

Figure 5. Free surface spectra, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ia55: $H_s=0.18\text{m}$ $T_p=5\text{s}$

Figure 6. Zero-moment wave height. Laboratory and numerical comparison – Regular wave cases

Figure 7. Zero-moment wave height. Laboratory and numerical comparison – Irregular wave cases

Figure 8. Pressure time evolution, solid line: laboratory measurements, dotted line: numerical results. Case ia55: $H_s=0.18\text{m}$ $T_p=5\text{s}$

Figure 9. Snapshots of instantaneous free surface, velocities and dynamic pressure

Figure 10. Wave overtopping as a function of time

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representing the percentage of overtopping wave. Comparison between numerical, semi-empirical and observed values.

Table 1. Target parameters for generated waves

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Figure 6. Zero-moment wave height. Laboratory and numerical comparison – Regular wave cases

Figure 7. Zero-moment wave height. Laboratory and numerical comparison – Irregular wave cases

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Wave type		Regular		Irregular
Wave height	H(m)	0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.225,0.25	H_s (m)	0.084, 0.12, 0.15, 0.18, 0.21
Wave period	T(s)	2, 3, 4, 5, 6	T_p (s)	2, 3, 4, 5, 6
Water depth at wave paddle	h(m)	0.8	h(m)	0.8
Water length at wave paddle	L(m)	4.89 to 16.56	L(m)	4.89 to 16.56
Wave steepness	H/L	0.00604 to 0.0511	H_s/L	0.005724 to 0.0429
Relative freeboard	F/H	0.8 to 2	F/H_s	0.95 to 2.38
Relative crest width	B/L	0.0604 to 0.204	B/L	0.0604 to 0.204
Relative wave height	H/h	0.125 to 0.3125	H_s/h	0.104 to 0.2625
Relative depth	h/L	0.0483 to 0.1636	h/L	0.0483 to 0.1636

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